

Utilisation of 2,6-dimethylpyridine by *Arthrobacter* sp.

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The strain Arthrobacter sp. KM-2.6DMP after 20 years of storage utilise the 2,6-dimethylpyridine at a concentration of 3.0 g/L.

Keywords: *2,6-dimethylpyridine, Arthrobacter sp., bacteria*

Introduction

Pyridine and its derivatives are an important class of heterocyclic compounds [1]. They are formed during coal processing and contained in wastewater chemical plants, plants of the production of synthetic rubber, plastics, dyes [2-4]. Pure pyridines are widely used as solvents and reactants in the production of agricultural chemicals, such as herbicides and also pharmaceuticals [5-10].

Materials and methods

The object of the researches served the strain of the bacterium *Arthrobacter* sp. KM-2.6DMP obtained from the collection of microorganisms of the Department of Microbiology, Moscow State University.

The culture broth was sampled in the course of growth of cultures analyzed, acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid to pH 3.0 and freed of cells by centrifugation on Beckman centrifuge (6000g, 4°C). 1ml of the supernatant was transferred to a flask, diluted to volume 100 mL of 0.1 N aqueous hydrochloric acid solution. The optical density was determined with a spectrophotometer Hitachi-200-20 (Japan), at the wavelength 268 nm. Obtained values were compared with the calibration curve the optical density of a series of solutions with different concentrations of the 2,6-dimethylpyridine prepared in 0.1 N aqueous hydrochloric acid.

Results and discussion

Activity of strain *Arthrobacter* sp. KM-2.6DMP to degradation of 2,6-dimethylpyridine after long-term (20 years) storage quickly was recovered to the level of 3.0 g/L, which had been prior to lyophilization 20 years ago (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Consumption of substrate (A) and biomass accumulation (B) with the growth of *Arthrobacter* sp. KM-2.6DMP on 2,6-dimethylpyridine.

On synthetic medium [11] with 2,6-dimethylpyridine in the early stationary phase of growth of bacteria was observed the formation of a pale-yellow pigment, which on the end of the stationary phase becoming intensely yellow. The intensity of the pigment synthesis was dependent from the concentration of added substrate (2,6-dimethylpyridine). When the concentration of 2,6-dimethylpyridine was 1.0 - 1.5 g/L then cells had yellow color, and the culture liquid remained of light yellow color. By increasing of the amount of the substrate to 3.0 g/L with one-time or fractional application the cells became intense lemon-yellow at the end of cultivation, and the culture fluid acquired a yellow-green hue. After separating cell from culture fluid that was transparent and fluoresces under UV light. Were evaporated extracts of culture liquid and acidified to pH 2.0-3.0 then it had an orange tint. Changes in the intensity of the staining of extracts according to the culture time was not observed. The structure and functions of the pigment is not revealed, and the pigment as we thinking have the nature of riboflavin. This

assumption is made on the basis that such formation and secretion of riboflavin into the medium have occurred during the growth of the strain *Arthrobacter* sp. on the synthetic medium with 2-methylpyridine [12]. These researchers suggest that such derivatives of riboflavin may play a role of cofactors on certain stages of the metabolism of 2-methylpyridine. In our case, the addition of riboflavin in a concentration of 1 µg/mL in the medium for growth of *Arthrobacter* sp. KM-2.6DMP increased rate of consumption of 2,6-dimethylpyridine in 1.5 times.

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